

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE 1. Color card of the colors referred to in this study (Color names were designated following the color nomenclatural code for description works of specimens in Kun L. Yang's private herbarium (HTBM)).

No.	Sample	Color Name		Color Code	Note
		Chinese	English		
\		瓷白色	ceramic white	#FEFEFA	Previously designated
\		羊毛白色	merino white	#F9F5EC	Previously designated
\		淡骨褐色	pale bone brown	#E7D5C7	Previously designated
\		深胡椒红色	dark pepper red	#764840	Previously designated
\		月黄色	moon yellow	#FAF9AA	Previously designated
138		深树莓红色	dark raspberry red	#B96F62	Designated in this study
139		亮石南褐色	bright heathered brown	#B9AB8D	Designated in this study
140		浅豆蔻绿色	light cardamon green	#ECFA9D	Designated in this study
141		淡豆蔻黄色	pale cardamon yellow	#F7F9D4	Designated in this study
142		淡土橙色	pale earthy orange	#F8E8C4	Designated in this study
143		浅柚木褐色	light teak brown	#BCAC84	Designated in this study
144		柚木黄色	teak yellow	#CDC79B	Designated in this study
145		浅豆蔻黄色	light cardamon yellow	#E9E9AD	Designated in this study